

IMPROVEMENT OF REHABILITATION TACTICS FOR CHILDREN WITH SEVERE FORMS OF CEREBRAL PALSY

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Purpose of the study: to evaluate the effectiveness of the outcome of nutritional rehabilitation on the course and prognosis of infantile cerebral palsy.

Materials and methods of the study. To achieve this goal, the results of treatment of 77 children with severe infantile cerebral palsy (ICP) aged from 2 to 17 years were analyzed. All patients were ranked by age groups according to the age classification of the GMFCS (Global Motor Function Classification System): 2-4 years - 14 children (18.18%), 4-6 years - 16 children (20.78%), 6-12 years - 27 children (35.07%), over 12 years - 20 children (25.97%). The studied group was divided into 3 subgroups of motor deficit according to GMFCS scale: level III - 18 children (23,38%), level IV - 22 children (28,57%), level V - 37 patients (48,05%) In the process of nutritional rehabilitation all patients were divided into 2 groups: main group - 41 patients (53,25%, age - $11,12 \pm 6,2$ years), in whom the complex of rehabilitation measures was carried out against the background of correction of protein-energy deficiency with enteral mixture, and comparison group - 36 children (46,75%, age - $12,13 \pm 4,03$ years), who received an identical complex of rehabilitation measures without nutritional correction.

Results of the research. 77 children with severe cerebral palsy - 40 boys (51.9%) and 37 girls (48.1%) were divided into 3 subgroups according to the nosologic form of the disease and peculiarities of clinical manifestation.

A retrospective analysis of obstetric and gynecological history of mothers of children with cerebral palsy was performed. Analysis of the timing of labor and the main parameters of the newborn showed a significant difference between the indicators of the main group and the control group. A statistically significant correlation was established between Apgar scores at the 1st and 5th minutes of the newborn's life and the subsequent level of motor deficit according to the GMFCS scale. The clinical and neurological status of patients with infantile cerebral palsy was assessed by studying the functional status. Characterization of functional status included a description of the child's daily activity according

to the GMFCS large motor function classification scale. GMFCS level IV is critical for the mobility of a child with cerebral palsy - 31.82% of patients with this level of motor impairment could not move even within their room; 22.73% of patients could leave the house with hand support. All children with GMFCS level V were practically immobile, and only 8.1% could move independently only in the form of crawling.

After a comprehensive assessment of the nutritional status of children with cerebral palsy, it was revealed that among spastic forms of infantile cerebral palsy, severe nutritional deficiency was observed predominantly in tetraplegia (6.49% of children), less frequently in diplegia (3.9% of children). Spastic hemiparesis was the most favorable prognostically: 82.5% of the examined patients had GMFCS level III.

It should be noted that regardless of the form of cerebral palsy there was a high percentage of children with swallowing disorders, which potentially created prerequisites for the development of nutritional disorders. Nutritional status disorders in children of the main group were aggravated by the following syndromes: oppression syndrome - 49 (63.64%) children, neuro-reflex excitability syndrome - 12 (15.58%) patients, convulsive syndrome - 17 (22.1%) children with cerebral palsy. Muscle tone disorders (hypertonus, hypotonia, dystonia) observed in the children of the main group contributed to the disruption of adaptation processes during feeding and eating, and directly depended on the presence and degree of delays in motor development caused by neuropsychiatric deficit with the formation of social insufficiency (limitation of self-care and movement). At dynamic examination in 6 months after the beginning of the complex of rehabilitation measures with correction of nutritional status, the growth rate of children with cerebral palsy in the main group was from 1.2 to 4.9 cm (Δ growth + 2.8 cm), while in children in the comparison group the growth rate varied from 0.4 to 1.6 cm (Δ growth +0.67 cm). It should be noted that all indicators characterizing growth dynamics in patients with infantile cerebral palsy against the background of nutritional status correction were higher than in children of the comparison group.

Conclusion: children with cerebral palsy are statistically more prone to very low physical development than children in the control group. In patients with cerebral palsy, disharmony of physical development occurs with a very high frequency and is caused primarily by nutritional disorders. That is why the positive dynamics of growth indicators is a reliable parameter of the effectiveness of rehabilitation measures against the background of nutritional

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correction. The conducted complex of nutritive rehabilitation promotes significant recovery of motor functions, a positive trend in reducing the need for special equipment and aids for sick children already at the first stages of rehabilitation.

